

Supplementary table 1. Overview of the literature review sources.

Author(s), nr. in manuscript	Theme	Short description including country, methodology and main finding(s)
		Consumer behaviour research
(Marx-Pienaar and Erasmus 2014), 24	Food provisioning	This is a South African study on the role of status consciousness and knowledge in fresh produce (fruit and vegetable) purchases. It is found that status consciousness is not high overall, but it is relatively high in four statements related to behaviors that could lead to greater food wastage. Low income and education respondents are more status conscious, but gender and age do not play a role.
(van Woensel et al. 2007), 25	Food provisioning	This study on consumer behavior in the case of bread out-of-stock (OOS) is based on 3,800 customer interviews conducted in three stores of a large Dutch grocery retail chain. The results show the consumers' high willingness to substitute; but there could be differences with regard to perishable and non-perishable items. Accordingly, the incorporation of such information into the existing automated store ordering (ASO) systems is recommended as this system is primarily designed and used for non-perishables.
(Yue, Alfnes and Jensen 2009), 23	Food provisioning	Experimental auctions in the US were used to assess the willingness-to-pay (WTP) for organic or conventional apples with different degrees of visual imperfections. It is found that consumers show little tolerance for visual imperfections, but those with higher environmental concerns are more tolerant. The WTP in the presence of visual imperfections decreases to a greater extent for organic than conventional apples. It is concluded that fresh fruits with visual imperfections have little market potential.
(Tsiros and Heilman 2005), 26	Date labelling	This is a survey investigating consumers' behavior in six important grocery stores in the Midwest and Southeast of the United States for perishable categories through developing a set of hypotheses and testing these using the PROC MIXED procedure in SAS. The results are: Consumers are less likely to check expiration dates for products with lower quality risk; the greater the category experience, the more frequently expiration dates are checked. The willingness to pay (WTP) for a perishable product decreases throughout its shelf life, this happens faster for products with a high quality risk. WTP is higher in situations in which consumers plan to stop the aging process.
(Van Boxstael et al. 2014), 28	Date labelling	This online consumer survey in Belgium concerns awareness of, knowledge about and stated usage of use by and best before dates on food. It is found that consumers vary their behavior depending on the food category in question: Some would eat products even though they have passed the use by date, while some would discard food that has passed the best before date. It is concluded that the shelf life date labels are not sufficiently understood and even misinterpreted, and it was discussed how the application of shelf life labels could be harmonized to make it easier for consumers to understand how to act upon it.
(Wansink and Wright 2006), 27	Date labelling	This is an experimental design with 36 subjects from the U.S. Army to study how freshness dating will influence taste and acceptability. This study concluded that freshness dating simply influences acceptability via perceptions of freshness itself and to a lesser extent, perceptions of the food's healthfulness.
(Kallbekken and Sælen 2013), 32	Food service	This paper shows with a very nice field experiment how nudging can be used to reduce food waste at restaurants (specifically buffets). Reducing the size of food plates and indicating that getting food multiple times is socially welcomed both reduce food waste significantly. This creates a win-win situation, as it benefits the environment and the hotel, while implementing such actions is relatively cheap, and customers remain satisfied.
(Hanks, Just and Wansink 2012), 30	Food service	In a US school lunchroom, a convenience line that offered only healthier food options nudged students towards consuming fewer unhealthy foods. Findings: Sales of healthier foods increased by 18% and grams of less healthy foods consumed decreased by nearly 28%. This line of research, i.e. nudging experiments, also points at the complex relationship between attempts to reduce food waste and to reduce obesity. The question is: Should we even define food as wasted if it is eaten? Should a definition of food waste not involve considerations of how much food we need to eat? How does this question relate to the introduction of optimal portion sizes/packaging? And how can consumers be urged to eat all the contents of smaller packages – but not to open others?

(Lombardini and Lankoski 2013), 29	Food service	This very interesting paper shows that policy interventions such as restricting food choices to sustainable options (a vegetarian day) have an influence on the food intake and food waste behaviors of consumers. More specifically, in the first six months of the policy, food intake decreased, food loss/waste increased, and attendance at such food places decreased. However, after six months, the only difference was a lowered amount of food intake (less food put on plates) but no longer an increase in food waste.
(Thiagarajah and Getty 2013), 31	Food service	This experiment tested hypotheses in an experiment where the impact of a switch was measured: Solid and liquid dining hall wastes were collected by trained personnel for 1 week (5 consecutive weekdays) while the then-current tray system was still being used, and for 1 week with the new tray-less system; this study shows a significant reduction of 0.81 oz. per patron in solid plate waste when compared to a tray system with a tray-less food delivery system in a university buffet-style dining hall.
(Wansink and van Ittersum 2013), 33	Food service	These findings suggest that people may have a visual plate-fill level—perhaps 70% full—that they anchor on when determining the appropriate consumption norm and serving size for themselves. Study 1 showed that dinnerware provides a visual anchor of an appropriate fill-level, study 2 shows large plates served 52% more, leading to 45% more consumption and 135% more food waste than those with smaller plates. Moreover, education does not appear effective in reducing such biases (study 3). Study 4 suggests that the Delboeuf illusion offers an explanation why people do not fully disregard this fill-level anchor and continue to be biased across a large range of dishware sizes.
(Whitehair, Shanklin and Brannon 2013), 34	Food service	This paper shows with one study that providing information on a restaurant's intention to reduce food waste is already enough to reduce food waste in an all-you-can-eat buffet restaurant on campus. Providing individual feedback does not have any additional effect. This indicates that an information campaign can work, although many studies report the opposite.
(Terpstra et al. 2005), 36	Household storage	Consumer interviews and observations in the Netherlands investigate the storage and disposal of foods in households. It is found that consumers do not necessarily behave according to their knowledge, and that correct handling differs between food categories. Refrigerator temperature is usually too high, vegetables are stored incorrectly, leftovers are kept for too long, date labelling is used to assess disposal even if it is no longer applicable after opening, parents of small children are especially attentive with regard to food for their children but not for themselves.
(Wansink, Brasel and Amjad 2000), 35	Household storage	This paper shows through a survey study that many consumers have unused products at home that they will never use and have stored deep within their cabinets. These food products have been bought for a special occasion or a special recipe which has never occurred. Consequently, the food disappears from sight and ends up in the bin after a while. Surprisingly, when consumers are reminded of these products, they do not intend to use them in the near future.
(Williams et al. 2012), 19	Food packaging	This Swedish household diary study on quantity and type of food waste focusses on the influence of food packaging, with half of the households having previously participated in an environmental education intervention. 20-25% of food is wasted due to packaging factors such as packages being too large, difficult to empty and having passed their best-before date. The educated households were less positive about packaging and packaging functions, and they wasted less.
(Bernstad 2014), 41	Food disposal	Swedish intervention studies in which households were provided with information on separated recycling of food waste were compared to the installation of sorting equipment. It is found that the information does not impact the quantity of source-separated food waste at all, which is why the equipment (hanger and paper bag) had a positive impact. It is concluded that convenience and habit are crucially important, and it was discussed that the equipment might also signal a social norm or serve as a 'visual nudge'/reminder. The type of message used in the experiment might not have been effective due to overestimating the households' knowledge, language problems and the timing of the intervention.
(Bernstad, la Cour Jansen and Aspegren 2013), 40	Food disposal	By providing oral information, the average source-separation ratio of food waste was increased while the ratio of incorrectly sorted material decreased in the food waste (excluding dry recyclables) amongst households.
(Comber and	Food disposal	This exploratory intervention study investigated installing 'BinCams' which post

Thieme 2012), 42		waste photos on Facebook in a number of UK shared households. Relative recycling achievements were measured and displayed, alongside survey and focus groups with household members. It is found that the interventions raise awareness and self-reflection, feelings of shame and realization of the attitude-behavior gap.
(Karim Ghani et al. 2013), 38	Food disposal	This paper applies Azjen & Fishbein's theory of planned behavior to the intention to recycle food waste. It uses one survey study with convenience sampling to demonstrate that in the first instance, all factors (personal attitude, social norms, perceived behavioral control and situational factors) correlate with the intention to recycle, but that in a multiple regression analysis, only personal attitude influences this waste behavior intention. Intention and behavior are very weakly correlated: 0.089.
(Refsgaard and Magnussen 2009), 39	Food disposal	This is a consumer and institutional study of two Norwegian municipalities, only one of which has implemented food waste recycling. It is found that the institutional context influences attitudes and behavior, with citizens trusting and feeling positive about the respective system installed in their municipality.
(Cappellini and Parsons 2012), 48	Households (practices, characteristics and motives, management) ¹	This is an ethnographic study including 20 households in the UK. Data was collected by a number of methods, such as interviews and observations of participants during mealtimes. The results of the study connects to the public discourses surrounding food waste, which often blame consumers and suggest that consumers who waste food lack "culinary competence", claims questioned by this research. Using up leftovers is a complex practice that involves a series of skills and knowledge. The ability to take care of leftovers is however dependent on the likes and dislikes of the whole family and their daily routines. The reuse of leftovers involves sacrifices by individual family members for the greater good of the whole family as well as collective sacrifices by family members, highlighting their membership to the family unit.
(Evans 2011), 45	Households	This is an ethnographic study performed in the UK over 8 months, involving the households of two ordinary streets in South Manchester. Data was collected using various qualitative methods such as in-depth interviews, "hanging out" in the participants' homes and "going along" when participants buy, prepare, handle and consume foods. The results suggest that consumers do not have a careless attitude towards the food they waste: Instead, this research suggests that food waste is a consequence of some of the ways in which domestic food practices are socially organized. In this regard, the author suggests that in order to reduce consumer food waste, the focus must be shifted from blaming consumers to making changes in the material contexts surrounding food waste. For example, if food was to be made readily available in different quantities (material infrastructures of provision), then the respondents in this study may well end up wasting less.
(Evans 2012), 44	Households	This is an ethnographic study conducted over 8 months, involving the households of two ordinary streets in South Manchester. The researchers traced how food becomes waste by close contact with the households and by collecting data through diary records, cupboard rummages and fridge inventories. The results of this study revise the thinking that food waste is a consequence of a "throwaway society" by exploring the dynamics of domestic food practices and by considering their consequences in terms of food waste. The results of the study indicate that: 1) the consumers do not have a careless attitude towards the food they waste. 2) Even though consumers feel anxiety because of generating food waste, most households do produce more food than they find use for and end up throwing some away. 3) In order to make sense of this contradiction, it's important to understand the social and material contexts of food practices, e.g. time, tastes, conventions, family relations and domestic divisions of labor.
(Farr-Wharton, Foth and Choi 2014), 51	Households	This paper shows in two different qualitative studies in Australia that food waste at consumer households can be based on the value-belief-norm theory. It shows that food waste occurs because 1. consumers do not know what they already have, 2. consumers do not know where they store their food, 3. consumers do not know whether they can still use specific food, and 4. situational factors.

¹ Studies characterised as theme 'households' are described in the manuscript with terms relating to practices, consumer characteristics and motives, and food management.

(Fonseca 2013), 53	Households	This survey study analyzed household food waste in Portugal with cluster analysis and a qualitative study. It is found that those with a higher likelihood to waste food are characterized by being young, male, and single.
(Graham-Rowe, Jessop and Sparks 2014), 47	Households	This paper reports a qualitative study of the thoughts, feelings and experiences of 15 UK household food purchasers, based on semi-structured interviews. Core categories of motives to minimize household food waste: (1) waste concerns and (2) doing the 'right' thing (3) food management skills. Core categories of barriers to minimizing food waste: (1) a 'good' provider identity (2) minimizing inconvenience; (3) lack of priority (4) exemption from responsibility.
(Koivupuro et al. 2012), 52	Households	This paper studies the factors that can influence the amount of food wasted in Finnish households. It uses both a survey to measure the possible factors and a diary study to measure household food waste. It finds that gender, household composition, belief in packaging, and value of money influence food waste. There is no influence from age, type of residence, education, and eating habits.
(Kriflik and Yeatman 2005), 49	Households	Australia, semi-structured, qual. interviews, n=26 food consumers. Findings: Health/safety outweighs sustainability concerns, but there was a strong conviction that a healthy environment was essential for safe food production.
(Stefan et al. 2013), 50	Households	This paper shows with one study that the theory of planned behavior is not very good at explaining self-reported food wasting behaviors. It demonstrates that the intention to waste food is not correlated with food waste behavior. Instead, behavior is predicted by planning and shopping routines. These two aspects are motivated by a consumer's attitude and perceived behavioral control.
(Watson and Meah 2013), 46	Households	This ethnographic UK study explores how different anxieties around waste and safety are negotiated in household food practices (ERC project CONANX). It highlights the conflicting responsibilities towards the environment vs. oneself/household members in terms of safety. It is found that consumers seem to rarely articulate environmental concerns, but are strongly driven by an innate ethic and motivation to be thrifty.
Author(s), nr. in manuscript	Theme	Recent reviews, overview articles or reports
(Brown et al. 2014), 69	Household storage and food waste	This UK review on foods' suitability for freezing also experimentally assessed the emissions of freezing versus the emissions of the food saved due to freezing. It is found that the majority of foods are suitable for freezing and that in most cases, freezing is relatively better in terms of emissions than discarding the food. It is concluded that consumers should be provided with better information on freezing and encouraged to do so with foods that otherwise would potentially be discarded as food waste.
(EC 2010), 56	Quantification and causes of food waste, Europe	The study identifies a multitude of causes, foremost sector-specific. For households, the study identifies "lack of awareness", "attitudes" and "preferences" as important causes for food waste, fully nutritious foods are by many discarded due to personal taste: e.g. apple skins, potato skins and bread crusts for example.
(EPRS 2014), 55	Overview food waste issue	The European Parliamentary Research Report summarizes food wastage data, trends, major causes and EU initiatives. The EU contributes 14% of global food loss and waste, with food waste on average per capita 180 kg. Household food waste is believed to be caused by 1) urbanization, 2) changes in the composition of diets, 3) globalization and large scale distribution, plus consumer culture (aesthetics, consumer behavior). There are crucial differences between the share of commodities when measuring in weight or in kilocalories (with fruit and vegetables versus cereals contributing most). Household food waste in the EU contributes with 42% and is increasing, while the total food waste is decreasing. The consequences are environmental, economic and societal.
(Evans, Campbell and Murcott 2013), 59	History of food waste issue	This is an overview of the history and current issues on food preparation, the relevance of food in society, and food waste. It does not focus on food waste prevention.
(FAO 2013), 11	Quantification and causes of food waste, world	This FAO study provides a global account of the environmental footprint of food wastage along the food supply chain. It answers two questions: What is the magnitude of food wastage impacts on the environment, and what are the main sources of these impacts in terms of regions, commodities, and phases of the food supply chain involved. It does not focus on food waste avoidance/sources of food waste.

(FAO 2011), 12	Quantification and causes of food waste, world	The results cover food waste globally, finding a higher waste in the high-income countries compared to the low-income countries and the highest waste in the end of the supply chain in high-income countries (at the consumer stage) and the highest waste in the front-end of the supply chain (in primary production and postharvest handling and storage) in low-income countries. No detailed studies on the causes of waste were made at the consumption stage.
(Fusions 2013), 54	Causes of food waste, world	This inventory explores the current food waste causes, the threats of increase and the possibilities for reduction in the future, recording a total of 597 items. Based on a qualitative analysis, this was reduced to 271 food waste drivers across all layers of the food supply chain and restaurants and consumer households. These causes can be divided into 5 main groups: 1. food waste related to the inherent characteristics of food products and the ways through which they have to be produced and consumed (perishability of food, limited predictability of supply and demand), 2. food waste related to social factors and dynamics in not readily changeable population habits and lifestyles (single-person households, young age of household members, couples with small children, increased consumption of meals out home), 3. food waste related to individual behaviors and general expectations of consumers towards not readily changeable food (good aspect, freshness, possibility of acceding to broad quantities, season, time), 4. food waste related to other priorities targeted by private and public stakeholders (the possibility of general food waste may be a minor concern with respect to other priorities of private and public stakeholders), 5. food waste related to non-use or sub-optimal use of available techniques, organizational inefficiencies of supply chain operators, inefficient legislation, consumer unawareness, scarce information, and poor food skills).
(Garrone, Melacini and Perego 2014), 64	Overview of food waste	This paper presents a complete overview of the sources of food waste in all aspects of the supply chain, offering a model that helps in understanding the chances of recycling that surplus. Its model is supported by 30 interviews and 3 case studies. It mainly focuses on the degree of recoverability, stating that this is dependent on the intrinsic recoverability and the required management intensity.
(Gentil and Poulsen 2012), 67	Overview of food waste	Here is an editorial stating (supported with numbers) that it is more useful to study food waste prevention than to study food waste recycling.
(Gjerres and Gaiani 2013), 58	Quantification of food waste, Nordic countries; ethics with regard to food waste	This review considers the quantity of household food waste, factors of influence and initiatives against food waste in the Nordic countries (Finland, Denmark, Sweden, Norway). In an ethical discussion, it is argued that food waste is mostly presented as an inefficient use of environmental resources and a lost opportunity for combating world hunger, which are both anthropocentric arguments. The issue makes people especially uneasy because food is perceived as a source of life, and in this religious wording, food waste is perceived as a 'sacrilege'. The authors argue that neither information provision nor moralizing can induce change, but this may be achievable with a different 'narrative' of the 'good life' and human-nature relationship in an eco-centric view, where food is not a product but a gift.
(Hoolohan et al. 2013), 72	Consumer actions for sustainability	According to the LCA/EIO analysis in this study, the three principal actions consumers can take to reduce GHG emissions are: (i) to reduce meat consumption, (ii) to switch the balance of meat consumption away from high impact meats (beef and lamb) to low impact meats (pork and poultry) and (iii) to reduce waste. Other smaller savings can be gained by avoiding air-freighted produce (i.e. sticking to fruit and vegetables that are either in season or have sufficient shelf life to allow travel by ship rather than aircraft). Finally, smaller savings can be gained by avoiding unnecessary packaging.
(Kummu et al. 2012), 65	Quantification of food waste, supply chain	This paper demonstrates the total amount of food loss and food waste across the world and across all steps of the supply chain. For every step in the process, it suggests ways to improve food production and reduce food waste.
(Labuza and Gunders 2013), 68	Date labelling and food waste	This theoretical argument for a more coherent system for food date labels claims (without having conducted any empirical studies) that these different date practices in the USA generate a lot of food waste and that this could be prevented by using one, government-regulated system.
(Milne 2013), 60	Date labelling and food waste, history	This theoretical paper describing the development of food date labelling over time in the UK links date labelling to food waste (stating that one of the causes of food waste is date labelling) but does not provide any evidence or further useful suggestions.

(Newsome et al. 2014), 61	Date labelling and food waste	This study showed that the terminology and applications of date marking vary widely around the world contributing to a substantial misunderstanding by industry and consumers and leading to significant food loss and waste. The work concluded that date labeling uniformity would have significant benefit. Food waste behavior can be altered through education, as a key component for this initiative, regarding the meaning of date labeling, the importance for some products of limited shelf life and temperature control, availability and understanding of food storage guidance, and safe handling methods. It also improves purchasing decisions by the consumer.
(Papargyropoulou et al. 2014), 2	Food waste hierarchy	This paper provides a general framework demonstrating how a surplus of food can move from prevention of food waste to landfilling. It gives very useful definitions of food waste and food surplus, avoidable and unavoidable food waste, and waste prevention and waste management. It does not provide any clear indications or ways to prevent food waste.
(Parfitt, Barthel and Macnaughton 2010), 10	Quantification of food waste, world	This is a review of food waste volumes and sources (UK, USA, but also Asian and other countries). Findings: Retailers' and consumers' demand for 'cosmetically perfect' produce has created significant post-harvest losses through 'out-grades'. Today's elderly people generally exhibit a 'waste not, want not' mentality, while the elderly of the future are likely to continue retaining the same attitudes and behaviors to food that they have today.
(Questa et al. 2013), 57	Food waste action overview, UK	This very interesting and relevant paper provides an overview of the findings of the WRAP campaign in the UK concerning food waste. They were able to reduce food waste in UK households for multiple years in a row, providing an overview of the factors playing a role. Mostly, this demonstrates that many different behaviors exert an important influence on food waste. Moreover, 1. food waste is not a conscious decision, thus requiring the unconscious level; 2, food waste only occurs after food consumption, and thus the focus should be on eating food rather than avoiding food waste, 3. there are generational differences, thus 65+ people should be studied, and 4. food waste prevention does not occur when emphasizing environmental benefits.
(Schneider 2013)	Food waste, definitions	The results show that many different definitions are used, and that the amounts of food waste vary between regions and between stages of the supply chain.
(Silvenius et al., 2014), 70	Packaging and food waste, sustainability impact	In Finland, LCA was conducted on climate change, eutrophication and acidification, while the amount of wasted food was estimated through a consumer survey. Findings indicated that the significance of the production and post-consumer life of packaging was relatively low for climate change, eutrophication and acidification, in comparison with the production chain of tested food (ham, dark bread and Soygurt).
(van der Werf et al. 2014), 66	Sustainability in the agriculture and food sector	The 34 papers in the review have been grouped according to different topics including: tools to guide producers and consumers in food-system decision-making and food production and consumption case studies.
(Wikström et al. 2014), 63	Packaging and food waste, sustainability impact	This Swedish experimental calculates the LCA for different types of rice and yoghurt packages and quantities of food waste that these create. The study explains that the usage phase of food products is often neglected in LCAs, and its result show that certain types of packaging seem more environmentally friendly in this kind of LCA, but the inclusion of the environmental impact of food waste substantially changes the LCA result, often in favor of other packaging. It is suggested that packaging attributes such as desired quantity, mechanical protection, easy to open, grip, dose and empty and food safety/freshness information should be included in simple scenario techniques when deciding on packaging.
(WRAP 2014, people focus)	Quantification and causes of food waste, UK	This report explores the relationship between the level of avoidable food and drink waste from households in the UK and factors including socio-demographics, behaviors and others relating to food, such as healthy eating and time available for food-related activities. It shows that household composition, age, fussy eating, time available for food-related activities, home composters, and perceptions of one's own food waste behavior are important influences on food waste.

(WRAP 2011, retail survey), 62	Food waste actions, retail sector, UK	WRAP's UK retail survey 2011 conducted store checks on 20 product categories believed to be prone to food waste, regarding product and promotion elements seen as crucial with regard to food waste, and the development compared to the 2009 survey. It is concluded that improvements can be observed due to many of the recommendations WRAP developed in 2009, as for example a decrease in 'sell by' and 'display by' date labelling, changes in the use of freshness date labelling, more information on freezing suitability and guidance, more smaller package sizes and functions such as resealability. However, some issues have not improved or worsened, such as e.g. in certain categories and for price gradients and price promotions.
(WRAP 2014, product focus), 43	Food disposal, UK	This report provides extensive details about household food and drink waste including detailed reasons about why it is thrown away, the size of individual instances of waste and the proportion of food left in packaging. It also provides details of which meal occasions are linked to the most waste and the percentage of purchases that are wasted. The most frequently cited reasons for wasting food are not being used in time (based on date, smell, or looks), too much prepared or served, and personal preferences.
(WRAP 2011), 71	Food disposal systems and food waste, UK	Overall, the literature review demonstrates that there is little available evidence to substantiate any firm conclusions that implementing a food waste collection will lead to a change in behavior around food waste prevention "at the source". There is, however, good evidence that there is a very considerable reduction in collected food waste overall (24% in the most convincing study). However, the extent to which uncollected disposal routes, such as composting, contribute to this is unknown and could well be significant.
(WRAP 2013, packaging), 37	Food packaging, UK	Here, a review is conducted of previous consumer surveys on food waste and packaging, of which 18 accompanied food shops and followed up through in-depth interviews at home and an online survey of 4,000 UK consumers. This study concluded that there are several improvement opportunities as currently consumers are not making the best use of the information on the pack or the packaging itself to achieve this, nor are they aware of the benefits that packaging can offer to maximize in-home shelf-life.

Reference list of sources not cited in manuscript but used in review:

Schneider, F. Review of food waste prevention on an international level. *Proceedings of the ICE - Waste and Resource Management* **2013**, *166*, 187–203.

WRAP. *Household food and drink waste: A product focus*, Project code: CFP204; 2014. Available online: <http://www.wrap.org.uk/content/household-food-drink-waste-people-focus> (accessed on 27 February, 2015).